

TRANSMISSION MOUNTED ON A BALANCER DETERMINATION OF CHARACTERISTICS OF PUMP JACK

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ABSTRACT

The substantiation of the possibility of using in the transmission instead of pump jack a V-belt transmission of a chain transmission is considered, and the issue of non-stop operation of pumping units during floods and floods, when the water level rises to the electric motor and a forced shutdown of oil production occurs. In this case, an electric motor with a transmission, which includes a gearbox and a chain drive, is installed directly on the balancer, and the connecting rods are connected at one end to the cranks mounted on the driven shaft of the gearbox, and at the other end are pivotally fixed to the frame of the pumping unit. Formulas for determining the torque and forces acting on the mechanism are carried out, approximate graphs are given.

Keywords: pump jack, transmission, V-belt transmission, chain transmission, balancer.

As a rule, a gearbox connected to the electric motor by the V-belt drive is used as the transmission in the rocking machines. The V-belt transmission in a pump jack has two purposes:

1) partial reduction of the number of revolutions, since the total transmission ratio of the pump jack transmission consists of the product of the transmission ratio of the V-belt gear and the gearbox, i.e., $i_{tr} = i_{cr} i_r$;

2) regulation of the stroke ratio of the boom suspension point with the help of replaceable pulleys, mounted on the shaft of the electric motor.

At the same time with the transmitted motor power N , the torque of the driven shaft of the transmission $M_{em} = N/n_{em}$ increases in proportion to the number of revolutions of the shaft of the transmission n_{tr} and motor n_{em} , i.e.:

$$M_{tr} = \frac{n_{em}}{n_{tr}} M_{em}$$

Despite the advantages of V-belt transmission, there are also some disadvantages, such as the comparatively short life of the V-belts and the low efficiency of the transmission and the extra little cost of machining the V-belt grooves in the pulleys.

An important prerequisite for proper V-belt transmission operation is that the belts have the correct tension. Insufficient tension of belts leads to decrease of their working capacity. Tension value of belts should be within known limits, exceeding which reduces their service life. In addition, tensioning belts above the limits causes an increase in pressure on shafts and bearings and thus leads to additional power consumption.

Considering these disadvantages of the V-belt drive, it was decided to consider the use of a chain drive instead of a V-belt drive.

In a number of cases, special requirements are placed on the construction of pump jack in the wells operated by the well rod pump method. For example, there is a necessity to reduce the volume of the core (foundation) in regions with frost and swamps. As the relief rises, the machines are flooded, and its electrical part remains under water, creating short circuits. This makes it necessary to install additional, special buildings in such areas. At the same time, designers are faced with the task of reducing the metal capacity of the designed equipment.

There is a construction of the swingarm, the transmission of which is placed on the balancer, which is protected by a US patent. Taking it as a prototype, a new construction invented at the "Oil-Mining Mechanics, Machines and Mechanisms" department of ADNA received a patent in 1990 [1].

The positive aspect of the pump jack is that the lower part of this construction can be periodically or permanently under water. Thus, its electric motor and

networks are protected from short circuit. The working principle of the construction is clear from figure 1. With chain transmission, the required tensioning during operation or loosening of the chain during a chain wheel change, necessary for the change of the boom swinging point, is obtained by turning the screw 15 of the platform 13 under the electric motor 11 around the swivel support 14.

Fig.1. Pump jack with transmission on a balancer:
 1 – balancer; 2 – balancer head; 3 – balancer support; 4 – stand; 5 – frame; 6 – foundation; 7 – connecting rod; 8 – connecting rod support; 9 – gearbox; 10 – crank; 11 – electric motor; 12 – chain transmission; 13 – turntable; 14 – turntable support; 15 – screw; 16 – rope; 17 – suspension of the wellhead rod

It should be noted that in this construction, the weight of the balancing counterloads is taken significantly less (metal is saved), since the transmission itself creates a balancing effect with its own weight. The difference between this structure and the US patent is that it is equipped with a second shoulder with a crossbar for placing a counter load. The advantage of this is that balancing is even better, as the connection points of the opposite load with the roller sleeve and the slider are located on different sides from the reducer shaft.

Consider the issue of synthesis of the mechanism (Fig.2).

Which indicates the ratio of the lengths of the arms of the mechanism a_1, a_2, a_3 and a_4 , as in the usual catapult bench syntize. That is, $a_1 = r/k, a_2 = r/l, a_3 = k_1/k, a_4 = r/p$.

Where k_1 – is the front shoulder of the catapult; k – is the back shoulder of the catapult; l – is the length of the slider; r – is the radius of the impeller; p – is the polar distance.

Fig.2. Scheme for calculating a drive with a transmission on a balancer

As a result of trigonometric operations, we find the dependence between these dimensionless parameters:

$$a_4 = \left[a_1^{-2} + (a_1^{-1} + 1)^2 - 2a_1^{-1} \left(\frac{-1}{2} + 1 \right) \left(\sqrt{(1-A^2)(1-B^2)} - AB \right) \right]^{0,5}$$

Where $A = \cos 0,5\delta_o$; $B = 0,5 a_1 (a_2^{-1} - 1) \sin\theta \sin^{-1} 0,5\delta_o$

Angle of tilt of the balancer and dizaxiality of the bench:

$$\delta_o = 2 \arcsin \left\{ a_1 \left[1 + (a_2^{-2} - 1) \sin^2 0,5\theta \right]^{0,5} \right\}$$

$$\theta = \arccos \left[a_o + (1 + a_o^2 - a_{o1}^2 - a_{o2}^2) \right]; \quad a_o = a_{o1} a_{o2}$$

$$a_{o1} = 0,5 a_4 (a_2^{-1} + 1)^{-1} \left[a_4^{-2} + (a_2^{-1} + 1)^2 - a_1^{-2} \right]$$

$$a_{o2} = 0,5 a_4 (a_2^{-1} - 1)^{-1} \left[a_4^{-2} + (a_2^{-1} - 1)^2 - a_1^{-2} \right]$$

The angle formed between the wheel arm and the rear of the catapult should be greater than the angle of rotation of the wheel arm: $\beta = \beta_o\psi$

Suspension point of barbells when starting to move upwards ($\psi = 0$):

$$\beta = \arccos\left\{0,5a_1(a_2^{-1} + 1)^{-1}\left[a_1^{-2} + (a_2^{-1} + 1)^2 - a_4^{-2}\right]\right\}$$

The angle between the balancer and the polar distance:

$$\gamma = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = \arctg\left[(a_2 a_4^{-1} - \cos \varphi)^{-1} \sin \varphi\right] + \arctg\left[(a_1^{-1} - \cos \beta)^{-1} \sin \beta\right]$$

The maximum value of this angle is:

$$\gamma_{\max} = \arctg\left\{0,5a_1 a_4 \left[a_1^{-2} + a_4^{-2} - (a_2^{-1} + 1)^2\right]\right\}$$

Here $\varphi = \arccos(A_1 + B_1 \cos \beta)$

$$A_1 = 0,5a_2 a_4 (a_4^{-2} + a_2^{-2} - 1)$$

$$B_1 = a_1^{-1} + a_2 a_4$$

The angle between the connecting rod and the crank:

$$\alpha = \arccos(A_2 + B_2 \cos \gamma)$$

Where

$$A_2 = 0,5a_2 (a_2^{-2} - a_4^{-2} - a_1^{-2} + 1)$$

$$B_2 = a_2 a_1^{-1} a_4^{-1}$$

When the crank is turned up to the angle ψ , the balancer turns up to the angle $\delta = \gamma_{\max} - \gamma$. Let's find the length of the dams of the mechanism. The length of the back shoulder of the balancer can be found by the following formula:

$$k_1 = S_0 / \delta_0$$

Length of remaining dams:

$$k = k_1 a_3^{-1}; r = ka_1; l = r a_2^{-1}; p = r a_4^{-1}$$

Let's conduct a kinematic analysis of the mechanism. That is, knowing the length of the rods, let's find the displacement, speed and urgency of the suspension point of the rods. Using the dependencies designated above, we will obtain the law of displacement of the suspension point in the following way:

$$S(\psi) = k_1 \left\{ \arccos\left[0,5a_1 a_4 \left[a_1^{-2} + a_4^{-2} - (a_2^{-1} + 1)^2\right]\right] - \arctg \frac{\left[1 - (A_1 + B_1 \cos(\beta_0 + \psi))^2\right]^{0,5}}{a_2 a_4^{-1} - (A_1 + B_1 \cos(\beta_0 + \psi))} - \arctg \frac{\sin(\beta_0 + \psi)}{a_1^{-1} - \cos(\beta_0 + \psi)} \right\}$$

To beat the speed of that point, we use the following formula:

$$V(\psi) = \frac{dS}{dt} = k \frac{d\delta}{dt} = k_1 \omega_m$$

Let's find the relationship between the angular speed of the balancer and the angular speed of rotation of the crank of the wheel.

$$\omega_m = \frac{d\delta}{dt} = \frac{d\delta}{d\psi} \cdot \frac{d\psi}{dt} = \omega_0 \frac{d\delta}{d\psi}$$

By differentiating the angle of rotation of the balancer with respect to the angle of rotation of the crank, we get the following expression for the speed of the suspension point:

$$V(\psi) = k_1 \omega_0 \left[(B_3 \cos \beta - 1)(B_3^2 - 2B_3 \cos \beta + 1)^{-1} + B_1 \sin \beta (A_3 \cos \varphi - 1)(A_3^2 \sin \varphi - A_3 \sin 2\varphi + \sin \varphi)^{-1} \right]$$

Here $A_3 = a_4^{-1} a_2$; $B_3 = a_1^{-1}$

Angular speed of the balancer: $\omega_m = \frac{V(\psi)}{k_1}$

The urgency of the suspension point: $W(\psi) = \frac{dV}{dt} = \frac{dV}{d\psi} \cdot \frac{d\psi}{dt} = \omega_0 \frac{dV}{d\psi}$

From here we get:

$$W(\psi) = k_1 \omega_o^2 \left[(B_3^3 - B_3) (B_3^2 - 2B_3 \cos \beta + 1)^{-2} \sin \beta + (A_3 \cos \varphi - 1) (A_3^2 - 2A_3 \cos \varphi + 1) (B_1^2 \sin^2 \beta \cos \varphi - B_1 \cos \beta \sin^2 \varphi) (A_3^2 - 2A_3 \cos \varphi + 1)^{-2} \times \right. \\ \left. \times \sin^{-3} \varphi + A_3 B_1 (A_3^2 - 1) (A_3^2 - 2A_3 \cos \varphi + 1)^{-2} \sin^2 \beta \sin^{-1} \varphi \right]$$

$$\text{Balancer's angle is urgent } \varepsilon_m = \frac{W(\psi)}{k_1}$$

The impeller of the pump jack's crank rotates around its axis at a constant angular speed ω_o and at the same time rotates around the axis of swaying with the catapult at an angular speed ω_m . Then the full angular speed of the crank will be as follows:

$$\omega_c = \omega_o + \omega_m = \omega_o \left(1 + \frac{d\delta}{d\psi} \right)$$

Model graphs reflecting the change of linear and kinetic parameters, built on the basis of computer calculations for one specific execution of the pump jack, are given in Figure 2.

Let's look at the force analysis of the mechanism. The following force factors affect the pump jack:

- P_o – variable force depending on the ψ angle resulting from the operation of the well equipment;
- P_M, P_R, P_W – the weights of the balancer assembly, reducer and counter load, respectively;
- F_M, F_R, F_W – the inertial forces of the assembly of the balancer, the reducer and the counter load, respectively.

Geometric parameters:

K_M, K_R, l_w – respectively, the assembly of the balancer and the distance from the center of gravity of the reducer itself to the wobble axis, as well as the distance from the center of gravity of the opposite load to point B.

The slider arm acts along the length of the quvand is calculated by the following formula:

$$P_p = \frac{M_{PO} + M_{EB} + M_{ER} + M_{F1} + M_{F4} + M_{F5} - M_B - M_R - M_{W1} - M_{F3}}{k \cos(\varphi_1 - \delta_1)}$$

Here $\varphi_1 = 0,5(\pi + \delta_o) - \varphi - \gamma_{max}$; $\delta_1 = 0,5\delta_o - \delta$

Torsion moment generated in crank: $M = M_{W2} + M_{F2} - M_{EW} - P_{RR} \sin \alpha$

The moments resulting from the acting forces are determined from the following dependences:

$$M_{PO} = P_o k_1; M_B = P_B K_B \cos \delta_1; M_R = P_R K_R \cos \delta_1;$$

$$M_{W1} = P_w k \cos \delta_1; M_{W2} = P_w l_w \cos \varphi_2; M_{EB} = I_M \varepsilon_B;$$

$$M_{EW} = I_W \varepsilon_B; M_{F1} = F_R^t K_R; M_{F2} = F_W^r l_w$$

Here: $\varphi_2 = \beta + \delta_1 + \varphi_o$; $F_B^1 = P_B g^{-1} K_B \varepsilon_m$

$$F_R^t = P_R g^{-1} K_R \varepsilon_m; \quad F_W^r = P_R g^{-1} K_R \omega_m^2$$

$$F_W^x = P_W g^{-1} \left[k \omega_m^2 \cos(\beta + \varphi_o) + k \varepsilon_m \sin(\beta + \varphi_o) + l_w \omega_m^2 \right]$$

$$F_W^y = P_W g^{-1} \left[k \omega_m^2 \cos(\beta + \varphi_o) - k \varepsilon_m \sin(\beta + \varphi_o) + l_w \varepsilon_m \right]$$

I_M, I_R, I_W – the balancer assembly, respectively, is the moments of inertia of the reducer with respect to the wobble axis and with respect to the output shaft of the opposite load.

The X_A horizontal and Y_A vertical reaction forces arising in the balancer support are determined by the following equations:

$$X_A = X_B + (F_R^t + F_B^t) \sin \delta_1 - (F_R^t - F_B^r) \cos \delta_1$$

$$Y_A = Y_B + P_o + P_R - (F_R^t + F_B^t) \cos \delta_1 (F_R^t + F_B^r \sin \delta_1)$$

$$F_B^r = P_B g^{-1} K_B \omega_m^2;$$

Here: $X_B = -P_R \sin \varphi_1 - F_W^x \cos \varphi_2 - F_W^y \sin \varphi_2$

$$Y_B = P_W + P_R \cos \varphi_1 - F_W^x \sin \varphi_2 + F_W^y \cos \varphi_2$$

The forces generated in the mechanism and the torsion moment were calculated in accordance with the parameters specified in the report and reflected in the model graph given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The torque generated in the mechanism (a) and graphs of their forces (b).

CONCLUSION

A design of a pump jack with a transmission mounted on a balancer is proposed. A diagram of the forces acting on the units of the pump jack with the transmission installed on the balancer has been developed. The derivations of formulas for determining the displacement, speed and acceleration of the suspension point of the rods of a pump jack with a transmission mounted on a balancer are presented. Formulas are presented for determining the forces acting on the units of

the pump jack. Geometric characteristics of the pump jack located on the balancer transmission have been determined.

References

1. Vagidov M.A. and Eyvazova Z.E. "Downhole rod pump drive". Patent No. 2005913. Priority of the invention dated May 3, 1990, registered in the State Register of Inventions on January 15, 1994.